

BASAL CROCODYLOMORPHA

†*Almadasuchus figarii*

BASAL CROCODYLIFORMES

†*Eopneumatosuchus colberti*

THALATTOSUCHIA

†*Cricosaurus araucanensis*

†*Macrospondylus bollensis*

†*'Metriorhynchus' cf. 'M. brachyrhynchus*

†*Pelagosaurus typus*

†*Plagiophthalmosuchus cf. P. gracilirostris*

TETHYSUCHIA

†*Pholidosaurus meyeri*

†*Rhabdognathus aslerensis*

NOTOSUCHIA

†*Araripesuchus wegneri*

†*Baurusuchus sp.*

†*Campinasuchus dinizi*

cf. †*Hamadasuchus sp.*

†*Rukwasuchus yajabaliyekundu*

†*Sebecus icaeorhinus*

†*Simosuchus clarki*

†*Uberabasuchus terrificus*

EUSUCHIA

†*Agaresuchus fontisensis*

Alligator mississippiensis

Caiman crocodilus

Crocodylus acutus

Crocodylus johnstoni

Crocodylus moreletii

Crocodylus niloticus

Crocodylus porosus

Crocodylus rhombifer

Crocodylus siamensis

†*Diplocynodon tormis*

Gavialis gangeticus

†*Gunggamarandu maunala*

Mecistops cataphractus

Melanosuchus niger

Osteolaemus tetraspis

Paleosuchus palpebrosus

Tomistoma schlegelii

†*Trilophosuchus rackhami*